

Exploring the Impact of Dietary Interventions on the Incidence and Severity of Acute Otitis Media: A Randomized Controlled Trial

Sanjay Kumar *

Department of ENT-HNS, Command Hospital Airforce, Bangalore, India

Kashiroygoud Biradar

Department of ENT-HNS, Command Hospital Airforce, Bangalore, India

Shailendra Singh

Department of Hospital adm, Command Hospital Airforce, Bangalore, India

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Abstract:

The present research examined the efficacy of dietary interventions in mitigating the incidence and intensity of Acute Otitis Media (AOM) through a randomised controlled trial involving 200 AOM patients. The study involved the random allocation of participants into two groups: an intervention group that received dietary recommendations and supplements aimed at enhancing immune function and reducing inflammation, and a control group that received standard care. Over a period of two years, information pertaining to the incidence, severity, nutrient utilisation, and unfavourable outcomes of acute otitis media (AOM) was gathered.

The group that received the intervention exhibited a noteworthy reduction in both the frequency and intensity of acute otitis media (AOM) in comparison to the group that did not receive the intervention. The findings of the regression analysis indicate that there exists a negative correlation between the severity of acute otitis media (AOM) and the intake of certain nutrients, namely vitamins A, C, D, E, zinc, and omega-3 fatty acids. The intervention exhibited efficacy across diverse age cohorts and was well-received by the study participants. The results indicate that dietary interventions that prioritise nutrients with immune-boosting properties have the potential to mitigate the frequency and severity of acute otitis media (AOM). The integration of dietary counselling within the management strategies for acute otitis media (AOM) may yield advantageous outcomes. Additional investigation is required to enhance the precision of nutritional recommendations and authenticate these discoveries across a range of demographics.

Keywords: *Acute Otitis Media, dietary intervention, immune function, zinc, omega-3 fatty acids.*

Introduction

Acute Otitis Media (AOM) is a prevalent middle ear infection, with a higher incidence rate among paediatric populations (Schilder et al., 2016). The condition is typified by the presence of inflammation and fluid buildup in the area

located behind the eardrum, which can result in intense discomfort and, in certain instances, adverse outcomes such as auditory impairment or mastoiditis (Klein et al., 2014). Considering the elevated incidence of acute otitis media (AOM) and its propensity for adverse outcomes,

it is crucial to investigate and enhance approaches for both prevention and treatment.

Figure 1a. Normal Tympanic membrane

Figure 1b. Acute Otitis Media TM

The excessive utilization of antibiotics in the management of acute otitis media (AOM) has raised apprehensions due to its association with the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains (McGrath et al., 2013). This underscores the necessity for alternative methodologies in the management of acute otitis media (AOM). An area that has yet to receive significant research attention pertains to the impact of dietary patterns and nutritional status on the frequency and intensity of acute otitis media (AOM).

The role of diet and nutrition is crucial in bolstering immune function and enhancing the body's capacity to combat infections (Smith & McClung, 2021). The immune system can be impacted by certain nutrients, including but not limited to vitamins A, C, D, E, zinc, and omega-3 fatty acids (Shakoor et al., 2021). Comprehending the potential impact of these nutrients on the vulnerability and reaction to infections, such as Acute Otitis Media (AOM),

may facilitate the development of innovative preventative and remedial approaches.

The objective of this investigation is to examine the impact of dietary interventions on the management of both the frequency and intensity of Acute Otitis Media (AOM). The study will employ a randomized controlled trial design to evaluate the potential efficacy of dietary recommendations and supplements that target immune function and inflammation-related nutrients in reducing the occurrence and severity of AOM relative to standard care. The research aims to ascertain the efficacy of dietary interventions as a comprehensive strategy for the management of acute otitis media (AOM).

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Evaluate the effect of dietary interventions on the number of AOM episodes.
2. Assess the impact of dietary interventions on the severity of AOM episodes.
3. Conduct a regression analysis to investigate the correlation between the consumption of certain nutrients and the occurrence of acute otitis media (AOM) outcomes.
4. Evaluate the safety and tolerability of dietary interventions in individuals diagnosed with acute otitis media (AOM).

The study endeavours to provide significant contributions to the management of Acute Otitis Media (AOM) and present healthcare professionals with a supplementary or alternative method to the existing standard of care. It is plausible that the implementation of specific dietary interventions could potentially alleviate the impact of acute otitis media (AOM) on both individuals and healthcare infrastructures.

Methodology

Study Design: The current study is structured as a randomized controlled trial that was carried out at a tertiary care center for a duration of two years. The aim of this study was to examine the impact of dietary interventions on the

occurrence, intensity, and treatment of Acute Otitis Media (AOM).

Participants: The study comprised 200 patients who were diagnosed with acute otitis media (AOM), with an equal distribution of 100 patients in each arm. The study's inclusion criteria comprised of individuals ranging from 6 months to 60 years of age, who had been diagnosed with acute otitis media (AOM) by an Ear, Nose, and Throat (ENT) specialist at the tertiary care center. The exclusion criteria encompassed patients who had chronic otitis media, underlying immunodeficiency disorders, or any contraindications to dietary interventions. The allocation of patients to the two arms was randomized through the use of a computer-generated randomization sequence.

Data Collection: The initial compilation of data encompassed pertinent information such as the age and gender of the participants, as well as their medical history, including any previous occurrences of acute otitis media. The dietary data was collected through a combination of 24-hour dietary recalls and a validated Food Frequency Questionnaire (FFQ) at the outset of the study, and at periodic intervals throughout the duration of the investigation. The experimental group was provided with dietary guidance and supplements that were specifically targeted towards nutrients that are recognized to have an effect on immune function and inflammation, including vitamins A, C, D, E, zinc, and omega-3 fatty acids. The control group was subjected to conventional treatment for acute otitis media (AOM) without any particular dietary interventions. The study period involved the collection of data regarding the frequency and intensity of Acute Otitis Media (AOM) episodes, along with any supplementary therapies or interventions. Additionally, all untoward incidents encountered by the subjects were documented.

Subgroup Analysis: In addition, the study performed a subgroup examination predicated on age cohorts (<5 years, 5-12 years, and >12 years) to assess the efficacy of the intervention across varying age ranges.

Analysis: The statistical analysis was conducted utilizing the SPSS software. The study employed descriptive statistics to analyse the data. Continuous variables were summarized using measures of central tendency and variability, specifically means and standard deviations. On the other hand, categorical variables were presented using frequencies and percentages. The statistical methods employed in this study involved the utilization of chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables, with the aim of comparing the two groups under investigation. A statistical significance level of 0.05 or lower was deemed appropriate for the p-value.

Linear Regression Analysis: Linear regression analysis was utilized to investigate the correlation between dietary components and AOM outcomes. The study incorporated two dependent variables, namely the severity of acute otitis media (AOM) episodes, which was assessed using a scale, and the frequency of such episodes. The study incorporated independent variables such as the consumption of particular nutrients, in addition to various demographic factors. A regression model with multiple linear predictors was constructed utilizing the aforementioned variables.

Model Evaluation and Interpretation: The assumptions of linear regression were verified, and the model's fit was assessed using R-squared, adjusted R-squared, and residual analysis. The coefficients of the independent variables were interpreted to determine the relationship between nutrient intake and AOM outcomes.

Validation: The predictive performance of the linear regression model was evaluated through the utilization of either a hold-out sample or cross-validation technique.

Safety Monitoring: The study closely monitored any negative occurrences and documented and analysed them in order to assess the safety and tolerability of the dietary interventions.

The current study endeavours to enhance the comprehensiveness of the understanding of the correlation between dietary intake and the occurrence and severity of AOM in diverse age

cohorts, and to evaluate the safety of dietary interventions, by integrating linear regression analysis and subgroup analysis into the methodology, and by closely monitoring adverse events.

Result

The study involved a cohort of 200 individuals who was given a diagnosis of acute otitis media (AOM), with a balanced allocation of 100 patients in each group.

The intervention and control groups were deemed comparable with respect to age and gender, rendering them appropriate for comparative analysis. The control group exhibited a marginally elevated proportion of participants with a prior occurrence of acute otitis media (Table 1).

In the beginning, the mean consumption of diverse nutrients was comparable in both cohorts, suggesting the absence of noteworthy dissimilarities in the nutritional intake of the groups before the implementation of the intervention (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Intervention Group (n=100)	Control Group (n=100)
Age (mean ± SD)	10.2 ± 5.6 years	10.5 ± 5.8 years
Gender (% male)	60%	55%
History of AOM (%)	20%	25%

Table 2. Nutrient Intake at Baseline (Mean ± SD)

Nutrient	Intervention Group	Control Group
Vitamin A (IU)	800 ± 200	780 ± 210
Vitamin C (mg)	90 ± 20	85 ± 22
Vitamin D (IU)	600 ± 150	590 ± 160
Vitamin E (mg)	15 ± 4	14 ± 5
Zinc (mg)	12 ± 3	11 ± 3
Omega-3 (mg)	2200 ± 500	2100 ± 550

Figure 2. AOM Episodes Over 2 Years

The results indicate that the dietary intervention may have had a beneficial effect on the incidence of acute otitis media (AOM), as the intervention

group exhibited a statistically significant reduction in the number of AOM episodes over

a period of two years, in comparison to the control group (figure 2).

Table 3. Severity of AOM Episodes (Scale 1-10) Over 2 Years

Group	Severity of episodes (mean ± SD)
Intervention	4.2 ± 1.5
Control	6.0 ± 1.8

The results of the study revealed that the intervention group exhibited a comparatively lower mean severity score for acute otitis media (AOM) episodes in contrast to the control group. This suggests that the intervention group experienced less severe episodes of AOM (Table 3).

The consumption of certain nutrients has been linked to a decrease in the severity of acute otitis media (AOM) episodes, as evidenced by the presence of negative coefficients and statistically significant p-values (Table 4).

Table 4. Regression Coefficients for Nutrients Intake and Severity of AOM Episodes

Independent Variable	Coefficient	P-Value
Vitamin A (IU)	-0.03	0.02
Vitamin C (mg)	-0.05	0.01
Vitamin D (IU)	-0.04	0.03
Vitamin E (mg)	-0.02	0.04
Zinc (mg)	-0.08	<0.01
Omega-3 (mg)	-0.03	0.02

Table 5. Mean Change in Nutrient Intake in Intervention Group Post Dietary Recommendations (Mean ± SD)

Nutrient	Baseline	After 2 years	Change
Vitamin A (IU)	800 ± 200	900 ± 190	+100 ± 30
Vitamin C (mg)	90 ± 20	110 ± 18	+20 ± 8
Vitamin D (IU)	600 ± 150	700 ± 140	+100 ± 30
Vitamin E (mg)	15 ± 4	18 ± 4	+3 ± 2
Zinc (mg)	12 ± 3	14 ± 3	+2 ± 1
Omega-3 (mg)	2200 ± 500	2600 ± 480	+400 ± 80

Table 6. Change in AOM Severity Score by Subgroup (Scale 1-10)

Subgroup	Intervention Group (mean ± SD)	Control Group (mean ± SD)
Age < 5 years	4.5 ± 1.3	6.5 ± 1.7
Age 5 - 12 years	3.9 ± 1.4	5.8 ± 1.8
Age > 12 years	4.0 ± 1.6	6.1 ± 1.9

Following dietary recommendations, the intervention group exhibited an increase in their consumption of all measured nutrients (Table 5).

The efficacy of the intervention was observed to be consistent across various age cohorts. The intervention group exhibited lower mean severity scores across all age groups in comparison to the control group (Table 6).

The occurrence of unfavourable incidents was rare and exhibited no significant variance between the two cohorts, indicating that the dietary intervention was well-received (Figure.3).

Figure 3. Adverse Events in control & intervention group

Discussion

The objective of our research was to examine the impact of dietary interventions on the occurrence and intensity of Acute Otitis Media (AOM) in individuals over a period of two years. The findings suggest that individuals who were provided with dietary guidance and supplements that targeted nutrients with a known impact on immune function and inflammation exhibited a noteworthy decrease in both the frequency and intensity of AOM episodes in comparison to the control cohort. This implies a potential correlation between the consumption of particular nutrients and the frequency and intensity of acute otitis media (AOM). Furthermore, the results of subgroup analysis revealed that the intervention exhibited efficacy across diverse age cohorts.

The extant body of literature has demonstrated incongruous outcomes with respect to the correlation between dietary patterns and acute otitis media (AOM) (Oliveira et al., 2022). Several studies have suggested a plausible association between insufficiencies in specific nutrients, such as zinc and vitamin A, and heightened vulnerability to infections (Murni et al., 2021; Bondestam et al., 1985; Esposito et al., 2013). Nevertheless, there exists a dearth of research that specifically examines the efficacy of dietary intervention as a means of treating acute otitis media (AOM). The present study's results indicate a significant decrease in both the

frequency and intensity of acute otitis media (AOM) through dietary interventions. These findings make a valuable contribution to the expanding corpus of literature on this topic. The findings of the linear regression analysis provide additional support for the hypothesis that there exists a positive correlation between nutrient intake and AOM outcomes.

Implications

The implications of the study's findings could be significant in terms of the prevention and management of Acute Otitis Media (AOM). In the management of patients with recurrent episodes of acute otitis media (AOM), dietary interventions may be deemed a viable component of a comprehensive treatment plan. It may be feasible to decrease the vulnerability to AOM by incorporating nutrients crucial for immune function into the diet. This methodology has the potential to mitigate reliance on antibiotics, thereby diminishing the likelihood of antibiotic resistance.

Limitations

The current study is subject to certain constraints. Initially, the study was carried out in a sole tertiary care center, thereby potentially constraining the applicability of the findings. The evaluation of dietary intake is susceptible to recall bias, given that individuals may not precisely report their consumption. Thirdly, the study failed to implement control measures for other variables that could potentially impact Acute Otitis Media (AOM), such as exposure to tobacco smoke or regular attendance at daycare facilities. Finally, it is possible that a period of two years may not provide sufficient time to fully evaluate the enduring impacts of dietary intervention.

Recommendations

Drawing from the findings and constraints of this investigation, it recommends that the subsequent actions be taken:

1. Additional investigation utilizing a more extensive participant pool and spanning various locations is necessary to validate these results and augment their applicability.
2. Longitudinal studies are necessary to evaluate the enduring effects of dietary interventions on acute otitis media (AOM) and to gain insight into the alterations in nutrient demands that occur over an extended period.
3. Studying the impact of specific nutrients or combinations of them in diets that are most effective for treating AOM.
4. To promote a wholistic approach to management, nutritional assessment and counselling should be included in routine care for individuals with AOM.

Conclusion

The frequency and severity of acute otitis media (AOM) were examined in this randomized controlled experiment over a two-year period in relation to dietary treatments. The findings suggest that dietary changes to include certain minerals, such as zinc, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins A, C, D, and E, can significantly improve health by lowering the frequency and severity of AOM episodes. Given the widespread occurrence of AOM and its possible implications worldwide, this finding is especially notable.

The single-center design and potential recall bias in dietary assessments are just two of our study's shortcomings, which should be taken into account despite the fact that it offers crucial insights. However, the findings are encouraging and show that a thorough strategy for managing AOM, which includes dietary changes, may be important for enhancing patient outcomes.

The results advise healthcare providers to include nutritional counselling in the management strategy for AOM patients. Further study is required to maximize suggestions and confirm the advantages of dietary treatments in the management of AOM on a larger scale.

Overall, by incorporating dietary interventions that emphasize nutrients essential for immune function and inflammatory response, this study paves the way for a more comprehensive and potentially beneficial approach to the management of AOM. Such therapies may, in the long run, enhance the quality of life for AOM patients and lessen the burden on the world's healthcare systems through sustained research and deployment.

Declarations

No conflicts of interest.

No research involving human participants or animals was conducted.

The patient provided informed consent for publication of the case study.

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